

INTRODUCTION OF E-GOVERNMENT AS A FACTOR OF BRINGING CLOSER THE DISTANCE BETWEEN THE STATE AND THE PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the development of electronic government, its importance in optimizing relations between the state and citizens, and bridging the distance between the state and the people. Also, it is scientifically based that the processes of introducing and improving the electronic government take place on the basis of 2 important factors - technological and legal factors, and that both factors have a parallel effect in the processes of introducing the electronic government. Based on the same analysis, the processes of implementation of electronic government in Uzbekistan are periodized from the point of view of the same 2 factors from 1991 to 2015, from 2015 to 2020 and after 2020. Also, the practical results of electronic government in our country in 2017-2022 have been systematically shown.

KEYWORDS

Electronic government, technological and legal factor, public services, "electronic participation", "one-stop shop" principle, ICT, online platform, electronic services, electronic cooperation, www.my.gov.uz, Unified interactive public services portal, 24/7/365.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the social, economic, political spheres of society, including the state administration system, cannot be imagined without electronic government. After all, electronic government serves to expand the capabilities of citizens through more efficient organization of public administration, quality delivery of public services to citizens, improvement of relations with business and industry, and access to information. The result is reduced corruption, increased transparency, greater convenience, increased revenue and reduced costs.

The concept of electronic government has been given various definitions and descriptions. In some sources, e-government is considered as the automation of the process of providing public services, while in others, e-government is defined as the use of information and communication technologies in the provision of public services to citizens, business representatives, state bodies and organizations.

The introduction of electronic government in public administration will not only change the traditional relations of governments with citizens, but also direct participation of every citizen who is not indifferent to the future of the country in public administration, in particular, to eliminate the problems and shortcomings that have arisen in society. It gives the opportunity to freely express suggestions and comments. In almost all developed and developing democratic countries, electronic government is establishing a comprehensive management practice for increasing the efficiency of public administration, quick and easy use of public

services by citizens and entrepreneurs, and their direct participation in public administration.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of electronic government first appeared in the United States in the early 90s of the 20th century. It is known that this concept arose in 1991, during the time of the President of the United States, Bill Clinton, when he paid special attention to the development of the Internet and information communication technologies in general at the state level. During the Clinton administration, the concept of "Electronic Government" spread to the mass media through the documents of state agencies, since 1999, began to appear periodically and frequently in leading publications across the ocean and in Europe. It was during this period that "Electronic Government" and related principles were analyzed and researched scientific works appeared.

In the UK, the Labor Party, elected in 1997, made e-services the centerpiece of its government modernization programme¹.

In countries such as the USA and Great Britain, which were among the first to pay attention to research in the field of IT, e-government is primarily understood as a concept aimed at increasing the efficiency of government activities². In particular, the concept of "e-government" was defined by Senators Lieberman and Thompson as a means of "using the advances in Internet technologies to improve the efficiency of government activities and provide citizens with simple

¹ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/e-government>

² Golobutsky A.P., Shevchuk O.B. Electronic

government. - Kiev: UMC-Atlant, 2002.

information about government programs, services, and information”³.

Electronic government is the application of information and communication technologies in public administration bodies, which is said to improve public services and democratic processes and support public policy institutions in harmony with organizational changes and the introduction of new skills⁴.

The term e-government is the use of information technologies by government agencies capable of reforming relations with citizens, businesses and various branches of government. These technologies can serve different purposes. These include improving the provision of public services to citizens, improving relations with industry and business, and more effective public administration. As a result, it is possible to observe the realization of advantages such as the reduction of corruption, the provision of transparency, the wide convenience of users, the increase of income or the reduction of costs⁵.

In the "Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on electronic government" adopted in 2015, electronic government is defined as follows. Electronic government is a system of organizational and legal measures and technical tools aimed at ensuring the provision of public services by the use of information and communication technologies to individuals and legal entities, as well as interdepartmental electronic cooperation⁶. Also, this law forms the legal basis for issues related to the deepening of administrative reforms in the state administration system, obtaining

specific results aimed at satisfying the demands and wishes of citizens. The principle of openness and transparency of the activities of state bodies, the provision of electronic state services based on the "one stop" principle, and the continuous improvement of electronic state services serve as an important guarantee of the realization of the rights and interests of citizens.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It is known from the history of the development of human society that the transition to electronic government, more precisely, the introduction of the system of providing public services in electronic form, goes parallel to the transition from an industrialized society to an information society. In particular, the role of ICT development is of primary importance. To put it simply, along with many aspects, the introduction of electronic government in a particular country requires the development of the technological aspect, along with many aspects. The results of the analysis of the Eastern and Western models of the introduction of electronic government also testify to this. With this in mind, the analysis of the experience of introducing electronic government in Uzbekistan first of all shows the need to consider the same process by dividing it into certain periods.

The results of the analysis of the experience of the leading countries in the introduction of e-government show that the processes of introduction and improvement of e-government in a particular country took place on the basis of 2 important factors. The first

³ Computerization of public administration// Bureau of International Information Programs. U.S. Department of State. - usinfo.state.gov , 30.10.2002.

⁴ Definition of the European Union to the concept of e-government.

⁵ World Bank's definition of electronic government.

⁶ <https://www.lex.uz/acts/2833860>

is the technological factor; the second is the legal factor. It should be emphasized that both factors have a parallel effect in the process of introducing electronic government. In this place, from the point of view of order, they were described one by one. Based on this, it can be said that in Uzbekistan, which became a sovereign subject of the international global community after gaining independence, the transition stage of the development of the individual society to the information society was under the combined influence of the same 2 factors. Based on the same analysis, the processes of implementation of electronic government in Uzbekistan can be periodized from the point of view of the same 2 factors from 1991 to 2015, from 2015 to 2020 and after 2020. Phase 1 from 1991 to 2015 can be described as the period of creating the necessary conditions for the transition to electronic government. First of all, this stage is distinguished by the entry of modern ICT and the Internet into Uzbekistan. We can call the second stage, which includes the period from 2015 to 2020 - the stage of development and improvement of "electronic government". At this stage, we can see the adoption of the legal document, which is the legal basis of e-government - the law "on e-government", as well as the improvement of the state service desk. The third stage, which includes the period from 2020 to the present, can be described as the period from "electronic government" to "electronic democracy" in the new stage of Uzbekistan's development. E-democracy - increasing the level of citizens' awareness about the activities of the government structure at various levels, openness of information and its delivery to the end user, support and strengthening of the two-way communication between the public and the authorities by the authorities and the public, Citizens' participation in public administration participation, direct support of democratic processes is considered.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

It is known from the history of the development of human society that the transition to electronic government, more precisely, the introduction of the system of providing public services in electronic form, goes parallel to the transition from an industrialized society to an information society. In particular, the role of ICT development is of primary importance. To put it simply, along with many aspects, the introduction of electronic government in a particular country requires the development of the technological aspect, along with many aspects. The results of the analysis of the Eastern and Western models of the introduction of electronic government also testify to this. With this in mind, the analysis of the experience of introducing electronic government in Uzbekistan first of all shows the need to consider the same process by dividing it into certain periods.

E-Government – service design that includes the use of the Internet and rapid electronic communication mechanisms such as instant surveys, web polls, and e-mail to provide government-citizen interactions with government services and transactions online and includes improving delivery.

E-Government can be considered simply as a website or online platform that can provide government services over the Internet. However, this would be an extreme minimization of the capabilities of e-government.

E-government can be conditionally divided into two types:

Electronic services: digital provision of services, programs and information by the government;

E-Participation: It can be said that digital communication related to the internet can increase public activity such as direct and indirect participation in public administration, voting, expressing opinions and even paying taxes, fines or various fees.

The introduction of electronic government in public administration will put an end to traditional bureaucratic obstacles, as well as increase the level of public services, simplify citizens' compliance with state legislation, increase their activity and trust in society, prevent corruption, fraud means reducing and increasing the efficiency of public spending. Institutional foundations of state administration bodies that do not meet modern requirements and the principles of their activity prevent the full implementation of the ongoing reforms and the achievement of the set goals. The introduction of electronic government in public administration is an important tool for creating a completely new, effective and high-quality system of public administration, organizing the harmonious activities of state administration bodies and local executive authorities in order to achieve the results of large-scale reforms implemented at the new stage of the country's development. . The main goal of introducing electronic government in public administration is to bring closer the distance between the state and the people.

In our country, based on the experience of information communication technologies and developed democratic countries, a number of works are being carried out to effectively provide public services to citizens by fundamentally transforming all sectors. In particular, as an implementation of the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 30, 2012 No. 378 "On measures to further improve the activity of the Government portal"

of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account the provision of interactive public services, A single interactive state services portal (<http://www.my.gov.uz>) was created and launched on the Internet on July 1, 2013. The purpose of this information resource is to create wide opportunities for users, and first of all, business entities to obtain information about public services, as well as to provide public services on the basis of the "one-stop shop" principle. The single portal of interactive state services incorporates the provision of services through the Internet, that is, the user has the opportunity to use interactive services of his choice from any point of the republic and at any time.

Today, the possibility of using 341 interactive services in more than twenty directions is provided, and the scope of public services is expanded and the implementation of their tasks is being further improved⁷. Through this portal, citizens of our country or business entities, representatives of organizations and institutions can get complete information on all elements of state power, and make official appeals to one or another state body in electronic form. The register of important interactive public services is also placed on the portal. A mobile version of the Government portal (www.gov.uz) has also been developed in order to create convenience for citizens.

Also, today, through this application, fast and efficient government services are provided for the population. The portal contains information on all issues related to the housing and communal services of Uzbekistan, tariff notices, and even a calculator for all communal services in a convenient form. Any person can post information and photos on the portal about one or another problem related to communal economy. With

⁷ <https://my.gov.uz/uz/site/statistic-graph>

the help of this information, relevant state bodies will study local problems and take measures to solve them.

In the process of reforming the field of public administration in our country, the creation of an operational system and digitalization of public services, which are convenient for the population, free from excessive bureaucratic obstacles, were set as a priority. In particular, during 2017-2021, new buildings of 142 state service centers were built, branches of state service centers were established in 129 regions. The provision of public services was reduced from 465 days to 237 days. More than 27.6 million services were provided through state service centers in 2017-2021, of which 11.4% were electronic (online) services. In addition, a total of 207 state service centers were established. The number of services provided through state service centers increased from 37 to 157. The number of documents required for the provision of public services has been reduced to 95. The number of mobile (mobile) state services was 662,411. In 2017, more than 170,000 state services were provided only to entrepreneurs, and in 2020, more than 8 million state services were provided to individuals and legal entities⁸.

Individuals and legal entities were provided 2,983 services in 2017, 1.3 million in 2018, 2.8 million in 2019, 3.1 million in 2020, and 9.2 million in 2021 through the unified interactive state services portal. 7 million state services were provided in January-July 2022. Today, 341 state services are provided electronically to individuals and legal entities through the Unified Interactive State Services Portal.⁹

Based on the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 7, 2015 "On measures to further improve the Government portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Internet, taking into account the provision of open information", more information is available on the Internet. Open data portal www.data.gov.uz was launched as part of the Government portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which allows free and free access.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

In short, the e-government will become a qualitatively new, truly democratic institution that implements the right to make political decisions in the management of state affairs, the basic rights of citizens: to receive and disseminate information, to express their opinion, and to participate directly.

Also, one of the main principles of the "Electronic Government" system is that every citizen can apply to the government at any time and place. That is, "Electronic government" means that citizens can interact with the state and access public services 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, regardless of their geographical location.

In addition, e-government creates the possibility of direct interaction with people living in remote or disadvantaged communities, as well as providing them with public services, identifying their problems and shortcomings in a timely manner, and helping them to eliminate them. . E-Government plays an important role not only in service delivery but also in

⁸ Results of the Strategy of Actions on five priority areas of development in Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 Fastbook: -Tashkent: Baktriya Press, 2021. 19 p.

⁹ <https://my.gov.uz/uz/site/statistic-graph>

strengthening digital literacy, digital integration, digital access and digital identity.

As a result of the practical implementation of these functions, the e-government can come closer to the realization of its goal. Also, building a system of full-fledged mutual cooperation of civil society, realizing these relations in a horizontal way, contributing to the rapprochement of the state and society, strengthening mutual trust, is the basis for increasing the value of the rights and freedoms of every citizen. is serving.

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